

COLLEGES DEANS' PERSPECTIVES ON FACULTY DIVERSITY IN UNIVERSITIES SAUDI 'S GOVERNMENT

SHARE AIYED M ALDOSARI

Associate Professor of Educational Leadership Educational Sciences Department, Education College, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, 54 Wadi Aldawaser Riyadh - Saudi Arabia.

E-mail: s.aldosari@psau.edu.sa,

Abstract

The study aimed to reveal the level of awareness of the deans of the faculties of the diversity of faculty members, and the level of knowledge Sharing Behavior (KSB) among the diverse faculty members. The researcher selected the descriptive approach; using a questionnaire distributed to an intentional sample consisting of (74) college deans in (4) emerging universities; They represent (15.61%) of the study. The results of the study revealed that nearly (80%) of college deans realize that diversity means the presence of diverse nationalities, cultures, religions and beliefs among faculty members, more than (60%) of them believe that one of the most prominent features of diversity is; exchanging ideas and getting to know different cultures, (44.6%) of them believe that one of the most prominent negative aspects of diversity is; the possibility of conflicts and disputes arising in the relations between expatriate professors and Saudi students, and (47.3%) of them considered that the most prominent challenges are the predominance of the number of certain nationalities and the possibility of bullying from them against the few expatriates. Regarding to the level of (KSB) among diverse faculty members; (43.2%) of the sample described its level as (high), while (35.1%) described it as (medium), and (21.6%) described it as (low). The study recommended enhancing the sense of belonging among expatriate faculty members, removing them from their rest areas, and making them accept new cultures, while convincing parents and students to accept them with their differences and diversity.

Keywords: Diversity, Emerging Universities, Knowledge Sharing, Different cultures, Expatriate Academics.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education, with its academic institutions, research and community centers, is the most important indicator of countries' progress and advancement, because of its significant impact on the development of life at all levels. Especially in the production and development of specialized knowledge, and the empowerment of professional skills, in order to provide outputs of high efficiency and quality.

Globalization has imposed new directions for the activity of higher education internationally, especially the developing countries, especially the Gulf Cooperation Council countries. Which seeks to emulate developed countries in adopting advanced higher education in the ranks of international university rankings. Globalization is pushing the world towards integration, which provides opportunities for intense competition, which has become necessary for institutional excellence." (Mahjoub, 2003, p. 6). Globalization also has a major role in creating new concepts of education, most notably; Distance education, open education, electronic university, educational satellite channels, educational platforms and their smart applications.

The great and growing demand for higher education; especially after the huge oil boom in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries to meet the needs of the labor market growing at

an accelerating pace; It was and still requires significant physical and human infrastructure. (Ben Ghanima, 2018, p. 18) It was necessary to attract qualified cadres from different countries and races of both sexes, regardless of religions, beliefs and cultures, to help and participate in achieving this goal. This had the effect of changing the culture of those countries and the heritage of their people, which led to the ire of some conservatives who resist change inside and outside academic institutions.

Despite the vast amount of research on leadership and student diversity, little has been written about deans and faculty diversity; Especially in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, but it is almost non-existent - according to the researcher's knowledge - in this specific field.

As for the distribution of faculty members by nationality in Saudi Arabia for the academic year, according to the statistics of the Saudi Ministry of Education (2019), the total number of faculty members reached (85,409), including (52,414) Saudi faculty members, representing (61.4%), And (32,995) non-Saudi faculty members, representing (38.6%) of the total faculty members.

As for the distribution of faculty members by sex and nationality, the number of male faculty members reached (50,568) members, representing (59.2%) of the total number of faculty members, including (28,640) Saudis, representing (56.6%) of the total number of male faculty members, and ((54.6%) of the total number of Saudi faculty members, while the number of female faculty members reached (34,841) members, representing (40.8%) of the total number of faculty members, including (23,774) Saudi women, representing (68.2%) Of the total number of female faculty members, and (45.4%) of the total number of Saudi faculty members. This means that the number of non-Saudi males reached (21,946) with a percentage of (43.4%) of the total males, and (66.51%) of the total non-Saudis, and (25.70%) of the total faculty members, and the number of non-Saudi females was (11,049) with a percentage of (31.8%) of the total female faculty, (33.49%) of the total non-Saudi faculty members, and (12.94%) of the total faculty members. (Ministry of Education, 2020).

Although the diversity of faculty members is one of the pillars of evaluation in universities according to the standards of international institutions concerned with quality and academic accreditation, the demand to localize university jobs in the (GCC) countries as a strategic goal for some of those countries makes the matter inconsistent, and even threatening the job stability of non-nationals from faculty members, and influencing their academic performance and organizational behavior. Also, making the renewal of their contracts in the hands of academic leaders through their personal opinions is a reason to control and dominate some of them, especially those who came from poor countries. (Al-Dosari, 2019).

An efficient and distinguished faculty member with a high qualification is the most important pillar of the university's success and competitiveness, in its launch process to achieve an advanced position in the international university rankings (Moore, 2005), regardless of gender, nationality or race, and this is a strategic goal for higher education to achieve the vision of Saudi Arabia. (2030).

Despite this, several studies indicated in their results that there are shortcomings in his professional and academic development in the various areas of his performance (education,

professional development, scientific research, community service, and administrative aspects) in Arab universities, including Saudi universities, and among those studies; The study of Abu Al-Rub and Qadada (2008), the study of Al-Aidarous (2009), and Al-Dosari (2019). Although, at present, global human resources departments are making great efforts when contracting with expatriates, whether in their selection or training (Tung & Varma, 2008)), and this has become a common management term with the connection of recruitment and orientation (Recruitment & Orientation) for the purpose of mixing Differing to form a coalition in favor of organizational work.

This is what was addressed by a study by Al-Dosari (2019), which adopted qualitative research, which sheds light on the current situation of the Saudi universities' contracting committees, which are still employing contracting faculty members (non-Saudis) through external commercial offices, and he aimed in his study at the same time to provide solutions to the issue ; that contracted faculty members from outside Saudi Arabia submit to Saudi universities directly from airports to classrooms; to educate Saudi students; Those who have different cultures and environments in many Saudi cities and governorates, and this is a bad model for appointment without any preparation, direction or prior preparation (Recruitment without Orientation), Al-Dosari presented a proposal for an academic protocol to be carried out by Saudi universities in cooperation with the Saudi cultural attachés in the contracting countries to address this imbalance.

With regard to the benefits of diversity of affiliates and members in institutions and organizations; It is of great importance for academic leaders to be aware that the diversity of faculty members is an opportunity to develop the Knowledge Sharing Behavior (KSB) behavior, in order to raise performance efficiency, increase competitive value, share different experiences and crystallize them for the benefit of the institution, and to support the efficiency of innovation in organizations, and this was confirmed by The study of (Fayyaz, Chaudhry and Fiaz, 2020), through which they sought to identify the factors that enhance knowledge sharing among workers, and contribute to increasing knowledge exchange processes, which would raise innovation rates and efficiency in organizations.

This study explored the relationship between; Enabling factors, processes, and outcomes related to knowledge sharing. Researchers have studied organizational level factors (top management support, organizational rewards) and technology related factors (ICT use) to show their relationship to knowledge exchange processes (collecting knowledge and knowledge distribution) and how knowledge exchanges relate to the level of innovation efficiency in organizations in Pakistan. Data were collected from employees of Lahore-based organizations, regardless of their field of work and level Hierarchy in the organization. The results of the study revealed that the support of senior management is very important in enhancing employee behavior towards knowledge exchange. However, organizational rewards and the use of ICT do not support employees in knowledge exchange activities. Knowledge exchanges are closely related to the efficiency level of innovation in organizations.

This study explored the relationship between; Enabling factors, processes, and outcomes related to knowledge sharing. Researchers have studied organizational level factors (top

management support, organizational rewards) and technology related factors (ICT use) to show their relationship to knowledge exchange processes (collecting knowledge and knowledge distribution) and how knowledge exchanges relate to the level of innovation efficiency in organizations in Pakistan. Data were collected from employees of Lahore-based organizations, regardless of their field of work and level Hierarchy in the organization. The results of the study revealed that the support of senior management is very important in enhancing employee behavior towards knowledge exchange. However, organizational rewards and the use of ICT do not support employees in knowledge exchange activities. Knowledge exchanges are closely related to the efficiency level of innovation in organizations.

Academic leaders' awareness of the broad concept of diversity helps them to make the best use of it, and enables them to improve competency at all levels of the academic institution. In the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia - where no university is ever devoid of diversity that may affect all elements of diversity - in a study conducted by Almuqrini & Mutambik (2021) on the explanatory power of social cognition theory in determining knowledge sharing among diverse Saudi faculty members, as a supposed academic community Awareness to invest the opportunity to exchange knowledge in light of the diversity prevailing in it at all levels. Where the study confirmed that the knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) works positively and significantly to improve academic education, scientific research and community service in universities,

Nevertheless, the level of practice in Saudi universities is low and does not serve professors, at the individual level, nor at the institutional level. The study revealed in its results the need for Saudi universities to hold seminars to demonstrate the strength of social cognitive theory to realize the importance of knowledge exchange. The researchers recommended the use of digital platforms for this purpose, perhaps improving expectations to increase knowledge exchange at the level of individuals and institutions in the Saudi academic community.

The high level of knowledge sharing behavior (KSB) is one of the advantages of diversity in universities among academics and needs more support and encouragement, whether they are from different countries in a country such as Saudi Arabia and other Gulf countries, or from one country; In the same country as most of the rest of the Arab and Islamic countries and other poor countries to which there is less emigration of diverse academic minds, whether this diversity of ideas, races, sex, nationalities, religions, or otherwise. in Pakistan; At the level of public universities - where Pakistani professors of other nationalities hardly mix but may differ in the rest of the other elements of diversity - in a study conducted by Bibi & Ali (2017) on the behavior of knowledge sharing (KSB) among academics in higher education, it aimed to verify the effect of motivation to share personal confidence, job engagement, job satisfaction, and continuity of commitment on the knowledge-sharing behavior of academics. The study questionnaire was distributed to (369) professors in (6) universities, the results of which revealed that (24%) of the independent variables of knowledge sharing behavior have statistically significant differences, and are due to internal self-motivation; extrinsic, personal confidence, and satisfaction; Job affiliation, and continuity of commitment. The study recommended removing obstacles to facilitate knowledge sharing among academics, and that

the academic leadership should provide academics with ways that would improve the level of job engagement, continuity of commitment and job satisfaction; For its role in supporting knowledge-sharing behavior.

Despite the foregoing, the diversity of faculty members presents challenges that institutions, especially universities, may face. In a study conducted by the researcher Almansour ((2015) on the challenge of transforming Princess Nourah Bint Abdul Rahman University in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from a local institution to an international institution, the study used the descriptive approach (case study), where this study dealt with this transformation case according to the challenges of cultural, economic and social diversity This study provides a broader understanding of the growing role of women in other Islamic countries and their participation in public life, and this study is an example for other national universities struggling to maintain a cultural, social and economic balance between local needs and global influences. The research led to a number of results, the most prominent of which are: There is no cultural problem within the institution among faculty members despite their different cultures, and I also mentioned that research at the university does not rise to the global level.

According to Hartel & Fujimoto (2000), the diversity of clients and workers in organizations will continue to increase in light of social, economic and global changes. This Japanese study confirmed that diversity is not a problem, but there is a problem in not being open to and accepting difference, and this in turn creates a set of opportunities and challenges in organizations. on whether interactions between diverse individuals result in benefits or losses to the organization; The researchers confirmed that this depends to a large extent on the level of openness to the existing difference and the organizational position on the exchange of knowledge and experiences between them. The researchers recommended tracking the structural and administrative characteristics that are expected to enhance openness to the difference in the workforce in organizations.

According to Hartel & Fujimoto (2000), the diversity of clients and workers in organizations will continue to increase in light of social, economic and global changes. This Japanese study confirmed that diversity is not a problem, but there is a problem in not being open to and accepting difference, and this in turn creates a set of opportunities and challenges in organizations. on whether interactions between diverse individuals result in benefits or losses to the organization; The researchers confirmed that this depends to a large extent on the level of openness to the existing difference and the organizational position on the exchange of knowledge and experiences between them. The researchers recommended tracking the structural and administrative characteristics that are expected to enhance openness to the difference in the workforce in organizations.

on the disadvantages and challenges of diversity among organizations; Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018) reported that parents of Qatari school students fear the effects of diversity in teachers on their children's conservative culture. On whether there is potential for conflict between members of diverse work teams Ayoko and Hartel (2006) conducted a study on leadership and cultural diversity, with the purpose of providing a new way of conceptualizing the role of the leader in conflict management in order to increase social tasks

and outcomes in culturally heterogeneous work groups, this is done by assuming the proposed relationships and quantitatively testing them using multiple regression. The results of this Japanese study revealed that the impact of conflict in culturally heterogeneous work groups depends on the way in which the parties involved in leading the work, whether at the level of groups, teams or institutions, and in particular group leaders manage. The researchers also conceptually identified some of the skills and behaviors related to effective leadership to increase the efficiency of the performance of culturally heterogeneous work groups. The model proposed by the researchers contributes to management, research and practice in three main areas; The first area, in the conflict management literature by extending it to the context of culturally heterogeneous work groups, especially cultural and ethnic distances and language-related conflict. The second area, in the leadership literature, by identifying the skills and interventions (attitudes and behaviors) required of leaders of heterogeneous work groups. The third area, in promoting an understanding of the interrelated processes between cultural diversity and social tasks and outcomes.

Although the managements of organizations strive to reduce conflicts within them by maintaining the focus of employees towards their goals and teamwork in light of their diversity and differences; Researchers Afzal, Khan, and Ali (2009) have found that managers are reluctant to intervene in a timely manner in employees' personal conflict. Moreover, employees at the same time are not comfortable with third-party interference, because they consider it their own affair. The researchers emphasized that since the inconsistency of relationships, resulting from diversity, negatively affects the smooth functioning of the organization; It becomes mandatory to address such activity at the overall root level, in order to prevent a negative impact on overall performance.

Fujimoto, Hartel, and Hartel (2004) also reported that adverse effects of diversity were often observed in working groups, but these Japanese researchers denied the availability of research identifying factors that lead to negative or positive effects in heterogeneous groups. In their study entitled: A field test of the mediator model of diversity and openness in newly formed groups. Openness to diversity affects the effectiveness of group decision and interaction patterns; The researchers uncovered a model of openness to perceived difference that provided one explanation for the process by which diversity influences group emotional, behavioral, and cognitive outcomes. This field study provided evidence that increased openness to perceived difference leads to better outcomes in newly formed groups. This implies the emerging universities to which the researcher's current study is intended.

In a study conducted by Al-Armouti and Hassan (2015) which aimed to assess the experience of Abu Dhabi University in managing diversity, by surveying the views of the 44 faculty members belonging to the specialized management program in human resources and financial management. The results of the study confirmed the existence of a relationship between the variables of using diversity strategies and good diversity management at Abu Dhabi University, and the results of the study showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the average degrees of faculty members' opinions towards diversity management among the sample members according to the variable (age, gender, nationality, specialization,

academic qualification, academic degree). The study recommended that the university continue to develop and implement its strategies and policies, which the researchers consider rational towards equality, justice and non-discrimination in dealing with faculty members.

On the relationship between leadership and team cohesion in educational organizations of different cultures and races; Wendt, Euwema & Van Emmerik (2009) conducted a study in which researchers hypothesized that there are direct effects of societal culture on leadership and team cohesion, in addition to the influence of leadership orientation that supports diversity and team cohesion. In this global study, data were collected from (29,868) managers as well as (138,270) members of work teams in (80) countries around the world. The researchers used multilevel analysis to test hypotheses linking individual and collective culture (IC), diversity-oriented leadership, and team cohesion. The study revealed that in “individualism” organizations, managers use behavior that is less directive and less supportive. Compared to organizations with a “collectivism” trait, the study denied that team cohesion is directly related to individual and collective culture (IC). But it did demonstrate that leadership's attitude and stance on diversity are linked to team cohesion; Positively and negatively, and this is most evident in the "Collectivism" organizations. In light of these results, the researchers discussed the implications of this in the field of education and the need to take care of leadership practices towards diversity in the teams of its institutions.

In a global study conducted by (Lisak & Erez, 2015) based on previous theories about the suitability of the person to the work environment and to the approach followed in the organization, the researchers hypothesized that emerging leaders in multicultural and multiethnic work teams score higher than others in terms of global characteristics or traits. The three are: cultural intelligence, global identity, and openness to cultural diversity. The researchers tested this hypothesis on a sample of (317) MBA students representing (32) nationalities, who worked in a four-week joint project in multicultural virtual teams from ten universities in eight countries (USA, England, Hong Kong, Germany, Italy, Spain, Switzerland) were part of a multicultural team project in 2009. Using logistic regression analysis; The results of the study revealed that individuals who scored high on the three global characteristics mentioned above were more likely to emerge as leaders than other team members.

In a study of (Ayoko, Hartel, Fisher and Fujimoto, 2004) on the efficiency of communication in light of the diversity of cultures and interaction at work through a comparison between Japan and the United States with regard to academic expatriates who worked as contractors between the two countries. The study revealed the suffering of these expatriate academics from racial discrimination - albeit hidden - in addition to racial discrimination against women; This is through unequal salaries with men under the university dome, in addition to the crisis of balance between women's work at the university and their family work, and these - according to their study - are the most important common features between Japan and the United States. Which in one way or another affects the academic work and reduces its quality.

The researcher believes that the results of this Japanese study with that comparison are important in the current study if we can link them with what is in force in Saudi Arabia; Where

there is no racial discrimination against women in salaries, and this is an advantage that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia excels in all fields and various educational institutions and others. Also, it is not permissible to pay a leadership work allowance to contractors, and some academic leadership titles do not apply to them, so the name of the contracting department head is (department supervisor) and not (department head), and he does not have a financial allowance like the citizens, and he does not have the right to compete for positions in the university. This leads to a lack of motivation to work for contract professors, and may also lead to the erosion of academic professionalism in universities; Especially the new and remote, in which the category of contracting faculty members abounds, and it may even cause the contractors to refrain from contracting in this type of university, and it may be a call for financial bargaining by some applicants wishing to contract.

In a study in the same regard, Sussman (2002) found that there is a gap waiting for contractors between working in their country and abroad; due to (Cultural Shocking) caused by alienation, cultural and moral difference, social level and lifestyle, Where Sussman's study included (113) American teachers who worked in Japan, the results of the research showed that they had trouble adapting when they returned to America and vice versa with regard to cultural identity between the two countries.

The researcher finds that this is noticeable and witnessed for his fellow contractors. Among those colleagues are those who are constantly comparing and complaining. He compares the positives of working in his country with the negatives in Saudi Arabia and vice versa when he returns to his country; Whether at the level of organizational behavior or academic custom. The culture shock and poor cultural adaptation that the researcher noticed on his fellow contractors, especially non-Arabs and non-Muslims, is considered an obstacle to full academic professionalism. Also, placing the fate of the contractors and renewing their contracts in the hands of the deans of the faculties often creates a psychological character that makes control and domination by them prevail in the relationship, which may lead to tension, disgust and resentment on the part of some contracting faculty members; While realizing the weakness of their regular position. Therefore, the researcher believes that this is a realistic incentive for the erosion of academic professionalism as an organized process, and this has led to the disruption of independence and freedom of opinion, which is the spirit of academic work.

On the same Gulf level, and in a study conducted by Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018), the researchers used the qualitative research methodology, which aimed to identify the views of general education school principals on the diversity of teachers in public schools in Qatar, given that expatriates represent approximately 72% of the population teachers, while 99% of school principals are Qatari nationals. Through this study, researchers sought to explore the level of these principals' understanding and understanding of diversity, their knowledge of the effects of diversity within their schools, the features of this diversity, the challenges they face and expected, and the issues that may arise as a result this diversity, and the mechanisms for dealing with it among faculty members with other contractors among themselves or with national teachers, as well as with students and their parents. This exploratory study in which researchers used semi-structured interviews to explore the views of (20) country directors;

regarding their understanding of diversity and experiences with teacher diversity issues. The sample included 20 principals, including (10) females, and (10) principals from (4) primary schools, (8) middle schools, and (8) secondary schools. The results of the study highlighted that managers face challenges that often focus on ethnic and cultural issues, and the study also revealed managers' discussions about how to manage issues of nationality, culture, and equality. She also noted that school leadership in a multicultural society such as Qatar requires more proficiency to manage teacher diversity. The study made many recommendations for school principals to work with a variety of teaching staff. However, the study did not cover higher education, which provided an opportunity for this current study to bridge this gap, in addition to the fact that many academic departments in emerging Saudi universities are headed by contractors, and this opens a horizon for deans to have a distinct concept of diversity from the concept of school principals who deal with teachers who do not They share power, as in the current study.

The study Problem

This study came as a result of what the researcher felt about the defects in his work environment in a number of faculties in which he worked with class; Among people whose affiliation is supposed to be science, and indeed it is the dominant feature of their other affiliations. But what the researcher saw is that the majority of academic leaders who contracted with these professors treat them in a manner that is predominantly of dealing with them as workers rather than academics. The students also leaked this behavior to the extent that some of them deal with the academic professor in a manner that lacks appreciation, and the matter even worsened when some of the contractors adapted to this character and this inferior status and went to the workplace in a dress that did not suit working in official offices; Not to mention that befitting the corridors of universities. This, therefore, leads to a failure to achieve the expected benefits from the diversity of faculty members in universities, and even leads to an imbalance in the quality of academic processes and, accordingly, university outputs. The researcher provoked the study of Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018), as it bears the issue of diversity of faculty members in the form of "public education" in a country that is one of the "smallest" countries (GCC), and this study came to fill the gap (gap) in the issue of Diversity is at the level of "higher education" and in the "largest" countries (GCC).

Study Questions

Through this study, the researcher seeks to reveal answers to the following questions:

- What is the concept of diversity in faculty members among the deans of faculties?
- What do college deans consider advantages of having a diverse group of faculty members?
- What do college deans consider as downsides to having a diverse group of faculty members?
- What do college deans consider as challenges given the diverse group of faculty members?
- What is the level of knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among faculty members in light of their diversity in all departments of the faculties that are academically led by these deans?

- How do college deans deal with diverse faculty members?
- What do the deans of faculties suggest to meet the challenges of diversity of faculty members and increase the positivity of their diversity?

The significance of studying

The significance of study stems from two aspects:

- Theoretical significance; the importance of the topic of study is "the diversity of faculty members", as it currently occupies an important position as a basic criterion in the success of most institutions, most notably universities.
- practical significance; It is represented in the high value of the expected results if they are taken advantage of, and then benefit from the diversity of faculty members in university institutions in the best way. It will also contribute to introducing Saudi universities, especially emerging universities, to the importance of investing in diversity and its role in the success of universities.

Objectives of the study

To reveal the level of awareness of the deans of the faculties of the diversity of faculty members; Understand, pros, cons, obstacles, and problems. In addition to revealing the level of knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among the various faculty members, in order to investigate the reality and monitor the expected trend, as well as shed light on what is hoped for.

Study determinants

This study is framed by the following limitations:

- Place; Saudi Arabia's Emerging Universities.
- time; January 2020-July 2021.
- human determinants; Deans of faculties in Saudi universities.
- research limitations; Deans' perspectives on the diversity of faculty members.

Procedural definitions

Many literatures have dealt with the definition of "diversity", the most prominent of which are the following:

Al-Armouti and Hassan (2015) define diversity as a term that refers to the differences that exist between members of the same organization; whether in terms of age, sex, and race, and religion, political or social orientation.

- When Hubbard (2003) tackled the definition of diversity, he divided it into two dimensions: the primary dimension; Including age, sex, race, and physical characteristics. The secondary dimension; Including educational and cognitive level, marital status, and income.

Al-Amiri and Al-Ghaliby (2011) defined diversity in institutions as: “The organization embraces pluralism and human diversity at work, and that the organization that supports diversity finds itself crystallized in what is called a multicultural organization, in which races, other demographic characteristics, diverse cultures and ideas mix.

Diversity can be defined procedurally as follows: It is the ethnic mix that exists within the multinational colleges, which resulted from the different nationalities of its employees, where we find local faculty members (Saudis) and foreign contractors (Egyptians, Jordanians, Yemenis, Syrians, Moroccans, Asians, Americans Europeans, etc.).

Study Methodology

Research design: In order to achieve the study objectives; The researcher applied the descriptive analytical method as the appropriate method.

Study population and its sample: The study community shall be composed of 474 Faculty Deans at 29 Saudi State Universities; A specific sample was selected from emerging universities where the diversity of professors is intensified by modernity; The sample consisted of (4) universities representing (13.8%) of Saudi universities, namely Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University (19) colleges, Jeddah University (14) colleges, Al-Jouf University (19) colleges, and Jazan University (22). The questionnaire was distributed to the deans of the faculties of the selected universities, which numbered (74) faculties. The (74) questionnaires were retrieved, i.e. (100%). Table No. (1) Shows the frequencies and percentages for the distribution of a sample according to experience in the position of dean:

Table No: 1

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	Deanship experience
20.3	20.3	20.3	15	less than a year
43.2	23.0	23.0	17	A year- less than 3 years
100.0	56.8	56.8	42	3 years or more
	100.0	100.0	74	Total

Table No. (2) Shows the frequencies and percentages for a sample distribution by type of college:

Table No: 2

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	college type
54.1	54.1	54.1	40	Humanity Scientific
100.0	45.9	45.9	34	
	100.0	100.0	74	Total

Table No. (3) shows the frequencies and percentages for a distribution of a sample by sex:

Table No: 3

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	Sex
52.7	52.7	52.7	39	Male
100.0	47.3	47.3	35	Female
	100.0	100.0	74	Total

study tool: After reviewing the theoretical literature and previous studies, the interview questions were formed and consisted of two parts; The first includes definition and data, and the second; It consists of closed and open-ended hypothetical direct questions at the same time for additions or rejection of proposals and recording a special answer other than what was suggested. Through the questions with the proposed paragraphs, the expected answers to the study questions were included, according to the researcher's knowledge of previous studies.

Statistical processors

Frequencies and percentages were calculated according to the respondents' responses to the interview questions.

Study results: presentation and discussion

Regarding the first question: What is the concept of diversity in faculty members among the deans of colleges? It is to give a comprehensive answer to it; This question was scattered in several questions, which are considered one of the vocabulary of this concept - according to the researcher's knowledge of global studies on the subject - and they were all under the umbrella of the mentioned main question, and the examinees made it clear that, and the first hypothetical question was; Does diversity in faculty mean that there are different nationalities, cultures, social and economic statuses, and abilities among faculty members? (59) deans answered with approval, ie (79.7%) of the sample members, while (15) deans answered with refusal (20.3%).

The second default question was; Does diversity in faculty members mean that there are different beliefs and religions among faculty members? 53 deans responded with the refusal, or 71.6% of the sample members, while 21 deans responded with approval, making up 28.4%. The third hypothetical question was; Does diversity in faculty members mean that there are different opinions and ideas among faculty members? (41) deans responded with rejection, ie (55.4%) of the sample members, while (33) deans answered with approval, making up (44.6%). The fourth hypothetical question was; Does diversity in faculty members mean the presence of other than what was previously mentioned in the previous hypothetical questions? (68) deans, or (91.9%) of the sample respondents responded with rejection, while (6) deans made up (8.1%) responded with approval. Their addition was (3) deans making up (4.1%) that diversity among faculty members includes The presence of different races, and (3) other deans also make up (4.1%) who added that it includes the presence of different races and nationalities. We note that those who agree to the first hypothetical question constitute the majority (79.7%), and this is strengthened by the rejection of the majority by (71.6%) and (55.4%) in the rest of the hypothetical questions with the possibility of choosing approval in more than one question. It

was added that diversity includes different nationalities and races, which means greater specificity. This reflects that the deans' concept of diversity is also diverse, but in most cases it focuses on different nationalities and cultures, as evidenced by the emphasis of those who added that diversity includes diversity of races and nationalities. This confirms that this overshadows this concept for them. This response is consistent with Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018)'s study of "public education school principals'" concept of diversity. It differs in that content from the study of Sussman (2002), which focused on the diverse upon their return to their countries and their cultural influence transferred with them as a result of diversity, and the study of Wendt, Euwema & Van Emmerik (2009), which dealt with diversity in terms of culture and intellectual direction in different countries.

Diversity in one country is not for diverse individuals. This distinguishes the study from others at the global level because it is in a country where the diversity of faculty members is an inherent characteristic in higher education institutions, and it probes the understanding of the academic leaders of colleges about this diversity. It also agrees with the study (Lisak & Erez, 2015) that emerging leaders in multicultural and multiethnic work teams score higher than others in terms of understanding and openness to diversity, and this current study exposed leaders in emerging colleges and all of them follow it as emerging leaders, especially after canceling contracts Leaders coming from prestigious Saudi universities who assumed these positions at the beginning of the establishment of these emerging universities in the last ten years in Saudi Arabia.

Regarding the second question; What do college deans perceive as advantages to having a diverse faculty? It was considered (49) deans who make up (66.2%) of the study sample that one of the most prominent advantages is the exchange of ideas and knowledge of different cultures. While (33) deans (44.6%) believed that creating a positive and successful educational environment that enriches the values of Saudi society is the most prominent feature of the diversity of faculty members in emerging Saudi universities, especially that they were created in modern societies with universities and academic institutions.

While (47) deans representing (63.5%) found that the most prominent feature of the diversity of faculty members is the availability of different perspectives that help in solving problems easily and correctly in emerging colleges and universities, as they are in dire need of this in this institutional phase. And (17) deans making up (23%) of the sample stated that bringing excellence in education and strengthening national identity is one of the most prominent advantages of diversity in faculty members. This study is consistent with that of Hartel & Fujimoto (2000); She emphasized that diversity is not a problem, but rather it creates a range of opportunities in organizations, especially if it is met with openness to it. The results of the current study differ with the study of Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018), in which the negatives of diversity prevailed so that diversity had hardly advantages, and perhaps this is due to the fact that their study was conducted on public education schools, while the current study is in the more mature and less threatening stage of higher education. before the beneficiaries, and because openness is a dominant feature among the employees of educational institutions at this level; Because the most universal sciences.

With regard to the third question; What do college deans consider as downsides to having a diverse faculty? It was considered that (33) deans who make up (44.6%) of the study sample that the possibility of conflicts and disputes arising in the relations between expatriate professors and Saudi students as a result of different cultures and a lack of understanding of the culture of Saudi society; It is one of the main disadvantages of diversity. While (22) deans, or (29.7%) said that one of the most prominent negative aspects of the diversity of faculty members in emerging Saudi universities is; Creating problems and conflicts for the existence of different religions / sects, especially since the societies in which these universities are located are Islamic, conservative and religious. While (21) deans representing (28.4%) considered that different nationalities impose their cultures on Saudis, bypassing or changing the local culture and traditions and affecting the national identity; It is the most prominent negative of the diversity of faculty members, and in this result it agrees with the study of Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018) where parents of Qatari school students fear the effects of diversity in teachers on their children's conservative culture. On the other hand, (10) deans, who make up (13.5%) of the study sample, added that the void left by the various faculty members, especially of different nationalities, when they leave Saudi Arabia, will represent a significant negative rather than a challenge that will have to be faced in the future because now in reality it still occurs through the termination of their contracts or Their resignations, and consequently, there are gaps in the institution at the educational and transactional levels. This is consistent with the study of Sussman (2002), which revealed that there is a gap of cultural, moral, social and lifestyle differences awaiting contractors between working in their country and abroad.

As for the fourth question; What do college deans perceive as challenges with such a diverse group of faculty? (35) deans who make up (47.3%) of the study sample considered that the most significant challenges are the predominance of the number of certain nationalities in one college or department and the possibility of bullying from them against the small group of expatriates, while this was excluded by (39) deans representing (52.7%) of the study sample. While this excluded (48) deans representing (64.9%) of the sample that providing strong effective and conscious leadership to manage a diverse faculty represents a challenge to manage diversity efficiently, while only (26) deans representing (35.1%) considered it a challenge and confirmed it, to differ with the result of a study Wendt, Euwema & Van Emmerik (2009) who demonstrated that leadership's attitude and attitude about diversity are linked to team cohesion; Positively and negatively, and with the result of the study of Al-Armouti and Hassan (2015), which proved the good management of diversity at Abu Dhabi University for its excellence in being rational towards equality, justice and non-discrimination in dealing with diverse faculty members, and in this it is a model to follow, as the current study agrees with Fujimoto's study , Hartel and Hartel (2004) field that provided evidence that the increasing openness to perceived difference leads to better results in diverse groups, and the researcher explains this difference that diversity is the dominant characteristic of workers in Saudi emerging universities and that they are implicitly the ones who run the colleges through their assistance to the deans and the division of working among them and implicitly leading the faculties and their departments; due to the dwindling number of citizens who teach in it; Where

it is spent on them in a number of college departments, even humanitarian ones, and even non-rare specializations instead of scarcity due to their small number, so this phrase was not considered as such, and it also differs with what the results of the study (Fayyaz, Chaudhry and Fiaz, 2020)), which revealed that the support of senior management is important Very much in promoting the behavior of employees towards investing in the diversity of faculty members, especially the exchange of knowledge. While (13) deans representing (17.6%) considered that the conflicts arising between different cultures, especially at the beginning of working together; It is considered the most prominent challenge that may face leadership in a diverse academic environment, such as emerging universities, and it excluded (61) deans representing (82.4%) of the study sample. This majority differed with the study of Afzal, Khan, and Ali (2009), which confirmed that conflicting relationships - resulting from diversity - negatively affect the smooth performance of the institution. (30) double their salaries in their countries; This phrase is not considered by the deans of colleges, because they are certain that the majority of expatriates comply immediately and adapt to any directive. Therefore, Saudi higher education is looking for expatriates from poor countries, and with this mechanism and its continuation without proper treatment; This may reflect negatively on the level of higher education and its future outcomes. (16) deans representing (21.6%) considered that making the diverse faculty members change the way they deal with students and parents to prevent conflicts between the various faculty members and between them and the students; These are the most prominent challenges, while (58) deans representing (78.4%) of the study sample were excluded. (10) deans, representing a percentage of (13.5), considered that preventing the various faculty members from playing a role in undermining local culture and traditions or trying to distort them; They are the most prominent challenges in the presence of a diverse group of faculty members, while this excluded (64) deans representing (86.5%) of the sample, because the current study differs with the result of Romanowski, Abu-Shawish & Merouani (2018), which revealed that the majority of the sample confirmed that.

It is clear from the previous results that there is a discrepancy in the responses of the sample and a difference with the previous studies, and a clear division in the opinions of the deans of the study sample, as there is no assumption made by the researcher who gained the dominant opinion or a clear agreement on their part, and there is also no addition that came to their minds and gained independence and support. Regarding the fifth question; What is the level of knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among faculty members in light of their diversity in all college departments? 32 deans representing (43.2%) of the sample described the level of knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among the various faculty members in their faculties as (high), while (26) deans representing (35.1%) described it as (medium), He described (16) deans making up (21.6) as having a (low) level, and with this majority of the high level of knowledge exchange in Saudi universities, it differed with the study of Almuqrini & Mutambik (2021), which revealed that the level of practice in Saudi universities is low, and the researcher explains that that The current study focused on emerging universities, while Almuqrini & Mutambik's study focused on all Saudi universities. Regarding the fifth question; What is the level of knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among faculty members in light of their diversity in all college departments? 32 deans representing (43.2%) of the sample described the level of

knowledge exchange behavior (KSB) among the various faculty members in their faculties as (high), while (26) deans representing (35.1%) described it as (medium), He described (16) deans making up (21.6) as having a (low) level, and with this majority of the high level of knowledge exchange in Saudi universities, it differed with the study of Almuqrini & Mutambik (2021), which revealed that the level of practice in Saudi universities is low, and the researcher explains that that The current study focused on emerging universities, while Almuqrini & Mutambik's study focused on all Saudi universities.

As for the sixth question; how do college deans deal with diverse faculty?

(36) deans representing (48.6%) of the study sample agreed that they deal in an equal manner between expatriate faculty members and local faculty members, regardless of gender, race, nationality or religion, and this result is consistent with the result of the study of Armouti and Hassan (2015). The researcher explains that the Gulf societal culture is almost one. While (26) deans, who constitute (35.1%) of the sample, stated that they deal in a fair manner, but they tend to distinguish Saudi faculty members over contractors (this has nothing to do with racism), and the researcher believes that this may have been a personal position, and it has nothing to do with professionalism that dissolves The differences in the harmonious professional academic leader. While (12) deans representing 16.2% of the sample stated that they deal in a fair manner, but they tend to distinguish expatriate faculty members from Saudis (i.e. prefer them to work), and the researcher believes that this category also may not have a vision yet and that the local cadre It is constant if it proves its efficiency and that diversity is an opportunity that must be invested in reducing the disparity in the levels of diverse faculty members to raise the efficiency of local people and empower them better for the future, and to meet the challenge of the vacuum that the departure of expatriates will create upon their return to their countries.

Finally, regarding the seventh question; What do college deans suggest to address the challenges of faculty diversity and increase the positivity of diversity? So (41) deans, representing (55.4%) of the study sample, have suggested; Enhancing the sense of belonging among the expatriate faculty member and his sense that he is coming to create a purposeful generation and help the country develop, not for the purpose of making money. While (22) deans constitute (29.7%) of the deans in the study sample, they suggested; Have faculty members change their attitudes and practices to align with Saudi culture. While (19) deans represent (25.7%) of the study sample, they suggested; Getting faculty members out of their safe areas and getting them to accept new cultures. and (13) deans representing (17.6%) of the sample, they suggested; Persuading parents and students to accept an expatriate/contracted faculty member with his or her ethnic, religious, nationality, or other diversity.

Recommendations

Based on the observed results, the researcher recommends the following:

First: At the level of the Ministry of Education; It is necessary to adopt the idea of a wisdom society, in which knowledge is employed, invested and produced, and this requires global participation, and the diversity of faculty members is a way to do so. Second: At the level of Saudi and Gulf universities; Where the diversity of its faculty members prevails over others in

its geographical surroundings in Asia and Africa, clear policies and specific explanatory regulations are necessary; It helps create an attractive academic environment that ensures the psychological well-being and quality of professional life of the diverse faculty, and guarantees their rights to organizational justice. In order to invest their presence to develop universities and improve their standing, and to develop the skills of their employees academically and professionally. Third: At the level of emerging Saudi universities; It is necessary to spread awareness among academic leaders such as deans, heads of departments, faculty members and employees about the concept of diversity, especially among faculty members, its advantages, challenges, disadvantages, and knowledge-sharing behavior (KSB). And that is through training, seminars and lectures, to invest diversity as an opportunity, and to deal with it to the fullest.

CONCLUSION

Saudi universities, particularly emerging universities, have the opportunity of diversity faculty. This opportunity is not available in a large number of countries, and creating an investment in this golden chance makes the challenges and threats raised around it a strength by the vigilant universities. Research is authentic through employing (KSB) theory for investing diversity in higher education particular in emerging universities where diversity is still the relative majority, and it's the gap found by the researcher in exploring the issue of diversity in previous studies. Some of this study results were unexpected, such as the need for expert leaders to manage faculty diversity, while the leadership style required for this task was harmonious (Resonant Leadership).

References

- Abu Al-Rub, I., & Qadadah, I. (2008). Evaluating the quality of the performance of faculty members in higher education institutions. *International Journal of Quality Assurance in Higher Education*, 42(6), 59-77.
- Afzal, H., Khan, M., & Ali, I. (2009). Linkage between employee's performance and relationship conflict in banking scenario. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(7), 19-25. DOI:10.5539/IJBM.V4N7P19
- Al-Aidarous, A. (2009) Evaluating the performance of faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University. The Sixteenth Annual National Conference, "Arab university education and its role in developing pre-university education", Cairo, University Education Development Center, Ain Shams University, pp.(246-176) .
- Al-Amri, T., & Ghalibi, S. (2017). *Management and business*. Dar Wael for Publishing.
- Aldosari, S. (2019). A proposed conception of contracting with non-Saudi faculty members to achieve academic professionalism in Saudi universities. *Journal of the Faculty of Education at Assiut University*, 35(5), 1-21.
- Almansour, S. (2015). The challenges of international collaboration: Perspectives from Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University. *Cogent Education*, 2(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2015.1118201>
- Almuqrini A., & Mutambik, I. (2021). The explanatory power of social cognitive theory in determining knowledge sharing among Saudi faculty. *PLoS ONE*, 16(3),1-24. DOI:10.1371/journal.pone.0248275

- Armouti, A., & Hassan, M. (2015). Evaluating Abu Dhabi University's experience in managing diversity from the point of view of a sample of university faculty members. *Journal of the College of Administration and Economics for Economic*, 7(3), 66-89.
- Ayoko, O., Härtel, C., Fisher, G., & Fujimoto, Y. (2003). Communication competence in cross-cultural business interactions. In D. Tourish, & O. Hargie (Eds.), *Key Issues in Organizational Communication* (pp. 157-171). Routledge.
- Ben Ghanima, M. (2018). *The politics of higher education in Algeria between the limits of funding and the challenges of development: 1962-2014*. Dar Al-Raya for Publishing and Distribution.
- Bibi, S., & Ali, A. (2017). Knowledge sharing behavior of academics in higher education. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 9(4), 550 – 564. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-11-2016-0077>
- Education Manistry .(2020) .https://departments.moe.gov.sa/Statistics/Educationstatistics/Docs/Table4-01_38-39.html. Retrieved in 25 December 2020
- Fayyaz, A., Chaudhry, B., & Fiaz, M. (2020). Upholding Knowledge Sharing for Organization Innovation Efficiency in Pakistan. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 1-4. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010004>
- Fujimoto, Y., Härtel, C., & Härtel, G. (2004). A field test of the diversity-openness moderator model in newly formed groups: openness to diversity affects group decision effectiveness and interaction patterns. *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*, 11(4), 4-16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13527600410797918>
- Hartel, C., & Fujimoto, Y. (2000). Diversity is not the Problem – Openness to Perceived Dissimilarity is. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 6(1), 14-27. DOI:10.5172/JMO.2000.6.1.14
- Hubbard, E. (2003). *The Diversity Scorecard*. Routledge.
- Lisak, A., & Erez, M. (2015). Leadership emergence in multicultural teams: The power of global characteristics. *Journal of World Business, Elsevier*, 50(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2014.01.002>
- Mahjoub, S. (2003). *Administration of Arab Universities in the Light of International Standards: An Applied Study for Faculties of Administrative Sciences and Commerce [Work-paper]*. Conference of the Arab Administrative Development Organization, Cairo.
- Moore, M. (2005). Distance Education: a Systems View. In M. Michael (Ed), *The American Journal of Distance Education* (PP. 129–132). Taylor & Francis Online.
- Romanowski, M., Abu-Shawish, R., & Merouani, N. (2019). Principals' perspectives on faculty diversity in Qatar's government schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 47(5), 730–748. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143218759089>
- Sussman, N. (2002). Testing the Cultural Identity Model of The Cultural Transition Cycle: sojourners return home. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations* 26(4), 391-408. DOI:10.1016/S0147-1767(02)00013-5
- Tung, R., & Varma, A. (2008). in, P. Smith., M. Peterson, & D. Thomas (Eds.) *Handbook of cross-cultural management research* (pp. 367-278). CA: Sage publications.
- Wendt, H., Euwema, M., & Van Emmerik, I. (2009). Leadership and team cohesiveness across cultures. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20(3), 358-370. DOI:10.1016/J.LEAQUA.2009.03.005